

Friction behaviors of carbon fiber tows and their effect on the manufacturability and mechanical properties of composite pressure vessels

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The friction behavior of carbon fiber tows is decisive in composite manufacturing processes such as molding, braiding, and filament winding by affecting the deformation and positioning of the tow. It is essential to consider the tow friction from the design stage, thereby allowing better control of process parameters and ensuring high product quality.

Herein, we propose a systematic framework that addresses the friction behaviors of CF tows and their impact on manufacturability and mechanical properties of filament wound composites through experimental approach. The results showed the significant multi-scale relationship between CF, tow, and composites in terms of their friction behavior and interfacial properties, directly related with manufacturability and burst properties of filament wound cylinders, which is not addressed through previous studies.

Material & Specification

Sizing agent	CF*	CF tow **
A	A_CF	A_Tow
B	B_CF	B_Tow
C	C_CF	C_Tow

* T700 grade CF with 1 wt % of an epoxy- or a polyurethane resin-based sizing agent

** 12k CF tow

- CF surface properties [1]

- CF tow microstructure [2]

Burst properties of filament wound cylinders

$$P_{Burst} = \frac{F_{2,max}}{2\pi rh} \quad \sigma_{Hoop} = \frac{P_{Burst} r}{t}$$

Friction behaviors of CF tows

<Modified based on ASTM D1894>

Future work & Final goal

- Quantitative study on the effect of CF surface properties and CF tow microstructure on the CF tow friction behaviors
- Computational approach to investigate the multi-scale behavior of filament wound CFRP

Consistency of CFRP manufacturing & Reliability of mechanical performance prediction

Manufacturability of filament wound cylinders

Related publications

- [1] Micro-scale study :
Lim, et al, *Composites Part A*, 2021;146:106424.
- [2] Meso-scale study :
Lim, et al, *Composites Science and Technology*, 2024;256:110786.